

Adapting Driver Drowsiness Detection Using OpenCV and Machine Learning

Alan Antony

Department. Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, India
alanantony2024@mca.ajce.in

Nimmy Francis

Department. Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, India
nimmyfrancis@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Drowsy driving is a common cause of accidents, particularly when traveling long distances or at night. A powerful technology that has the potential to greatly reduce the risk of accidents caused by drowsy driving is the application of machine learning, specifically Deep Learning with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), and OpenCV for driver drowsiness detection. In order to track facial landmarks, this system records live video of the driver's face using a camera and processes it using OpenCV. After analyzing this data, a machine learning algorithm determines the driver's level of alertness and, if necessary, sounds or visually alerts them if they start to get sleepy. This technology can prevent distracted driving accidents by promptly alerting drivers to their drowsiness, ultimately improving road safety.

Keywords— Driver Drowsiness Detection, Machine Learning, OpenCV, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Deep Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Especially for long-distance driving, the driver drowsiness detection system makes use of computer vision and machine learning technologies to improve road safety. Thanks to developments in machine learning and computer vision, it is now possible to develop systems that use video data to accurately identify driver drowsiness in real-time. A popular computer vision library called OpenCV provides a wide range of tools and techniques for processing and analyzing video data. It can recognize expressions on the face, such as the movements of the mouth and eyes, which are important markers of driver fatigue. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), a type of machine learning algorithm, and OpenCV can be used to create robust and accurate drowsiness detection systems that can be installed in cars or integrated into pre-existing driver assistance systems.

Challenges

i. Data collection: The collection of data is a major barrier to developing a driver drowsiness detection system. It can be difficult to obtain a sizable and diverse dataset that accurately captures the whole range of operating conditions for the system.

ii. Variability in driver behavior: People display different types of behavior when they are sleepy. For example, some people may blink more frequently, while others may react more slowly or exhibit other visible symptoms. This diversity presents a challenge in the effort to develop a model that can accurately detect drowsiness in every person.

iii. Environmental factors: Factors such as lighting, road surface conditions and other environmental factors are just a few examples of the elements that can affect how effective a driver drowsiness detection system is.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Rode, Manoj, et.al in [1]: The proposed driver drowsiness detection system integrates the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) algorithm and machine learning methods, with a focus on improving car safety by mitigating the risks associated with driver fatigue. The system's core functionality is based on OpenCV, which enables the extraction of facial features and the Region of Interest (ROI), specifically the driver's eyes, from a continuous stream of images captured by a webcam. The EAR algorithm is applied to assess the status of the driver's eyes, determining whether they are open or closed. By utilizing this approach, the system effectively alerts the driver when signs of drowsiness are detected. Beyond its application in the context of road safety, the versatility of this model extends to other industries, such as military, manufacturing, office environments, and transportation sectors, where drowsiness detection is of paramount importance.

Rahul Thakur, Shivam, Shubham Raj, Subhanshu Pandey et. Al in [2]: A major global threat, sleepy driving is responsible for many traffic accidents. This study presents a machine learning-based real-time driver drowsiness detection system. The system detects faces using OpenCV functions and recognizes facial features using the Haar Cascade classifier. Its main objective is to identify early indicators of drowsiness in the driver by evaluating the open/closed state of the driver's eyes and subsequently warning them. Even though researchers have looked into a number of distraction detection strategies, including eye blinking and yawning detection, sleepy driving is still a common problem, with fatigue and carelessness being blamed for many accidents.

With a 95.78% accuracy rate in tests, the deep convolutional neural network (CNN) model for accurate detection presented in the study is a promising way to reduce the risks associated with sleepy driving. By advancing the field of driver alertness systems, this study helps to prevent accidents and improve traffic safety.

George, Anjith, and Aurobinda Routray. et.al in [3]. Estimating the direction of gaze is essential for many applications, particularly in HCI. In the past, gaze was determined using geometric relations and facial features. However, gaze estimation and eye detection have been completely transformed by developments in deep learning, especially with regard to Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). CNNs can accurately and efficiently extract complex features from eye images. Using algorithms like Viola-Jones, modern methods can detect faces and use CNNs to predict gaze directions. More natural human-computer interactions are now possible thanks to these real-time frameworks that make eye gaze tracking accessible for uses ranging from information retrieval to augmented reality. They constitute an important advancement in the field due to their low computational complexity and compatibility with off-the-shelf cameras.

Kumar, Ashish, and Rusha Patra. et.al in [4]. This work presents a real-time, low-cost drowsiness detection system based on image processing and a webcam. It uses facial landmark analysis and face detection to compute metrics such as head position, mouth opening ratio, and aspect ratio of the eyes. Using support vector machine-based classification and adaptive thresholding, the system shows encouraging results with 100% specificity and 95.58% sensitivity. The review highlights the advantages and disadvantages of the three categories into which current drowsiness detection techniques fall: physiological, behavioral, and vehicle-based. The suggested system is a practical way to address the important problem of driver fatigue on the roads because it is portable and non-intrusive.

Elena Magán, M. Paz Sesmero, Juan Manuel Alonso-Weber, and Araceli Sanchis et.al in [5]. The Advanced Driver Assistance System (ADAS), which aims to prevent traffic accidents by detecting driver drowsiness, is introduced in this paper. It uses a 60-second video clip centered on the driver's face to detect indicators of fatigue. The system provides two solutions: one that makes use of fuzzy logic and deep learning techniques, and the other that is based on recurrent and convolutional neural networks. During training and testing, both systems achieved similar accuracy rates of about 65% and 60%, respectively. Interestingly, the fuzzy logic-based approach successfully reduced false alarms while demonstrating a greater specificity of 93%. This system outperformed many prior algorithms with an impressive accuracy of 96.8% at a speed of 8.4 frames per second. Moreover, trials conducted using a customized dataset demonstrated its usefulness in intelligent transportation systems.

III. METHODOLOGY

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ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2023, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

The code is used to implement a driver drowsiness detection system using Pygame, OpenCV, and Keras. Using a webcam feed to track a driver's eyes in real time, this system attempts to detect when a driver is sleepy.

Data Gathering:

Create a dataset with pictures of eyes that are open and closed. The folder named open contains the eyes open images and the folder named closed contains eyes closed images.

Model Instruction:

Make use of the acquired dataset to train a convolutional neural network (CNN). The two convolutional layers in the CNN architecture are used for feature extraction.

- Max-pooling layers to reduce the feature maps' sample size.
- Eliminate layers to avoid overfitting.
- A thick layer intended for categorization.

Real-time Drowsiness Detection:

- Record webcam video frames using OpenCV.
- Grayscale the frames as part of the data processing process.
- To identify the driver's face, left eye, and right eye regions in every frame, use Haar cascades.

Classification of Eyes:

For every identified eye region:

- Resize and normalize the eye image to 24 x 24 pixels as part of the preprocessing steps.
- Using the trained CNN model, determine if the eye is open or closed.
- Record the number of consecutive frames in which the eyes are closed as well as the state (open or closed).

Alert for Drowsiness:

Set an alarm to notify the driver if both eyes stay closed for a predetermined amount of time.

Use Pygame's mixer feature to optionally change the video frame's appearance or trigger an alarm.

In order to improve road safety, this methodology modifies the given code and model to create a real-time driver drowsiness detection system.

Haar Cascades

Haar cascades are essential tools in object detection, particularly in recognizing facial features in a video stream, like the face and eyes. These cascades make use of pre-trained classifiers that make use of Haar-like features basically, rectangular boxes with position, size, and shape

characteristics. They are essential for identifying regions in an image that are most likely to contain the object of interest.

Training a machine learning model on a large dataset of both positive and negative images is the first step in creating Haar cascades. While the negative images show various unimportant objects or backgrounds, the positive images show instances of the object to be detected. The model can identify the most pertinent Haar-like features for accurate object detection thanks to this training process.

Haar cascades are used in the drowsiness detection system to identify the person's face and eyes in the video stream. This tactical move enables the system to focus on the area surrounding the eyes, which frequently display obvious indicators of tiredness. The pre-trained Haar cascades are loaded along with other necessary libraries and models in the first step of the procedure.

Convolutional Neural Network

An important component of the drowsiness detection system's architecture is a convolutional neural network (CNN). This particular neural network variant is made to differentiate between two categories in images: those with open eyes and those with closed eyes. The CNN is an example of a deep learning model that has been thoroughly trained on a large dataset that includes pictures of both open and closed eyes.

The CNN learns through training to identify complex patterns and distinguishing characteristics that separate open from closed eyes. This well-trained CNN model is then incorporated into the code during the first loading stage after training is finished. It then actively participates in the following steps to determine whether the eyes in the video frame or input image are open or closed.

SoftMax

A popular activation function in the output layer of neural networks, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), is the softmax algorithm. Its main job is to convert the output of the neural network into a probability distribution that includes several classes. The softmax algorithm is a key component of the CNN's output layer in the drowsiness detection system's code.

It is specifically useful in classifying the input image into two groups: those with open eyes and those with closed eyes. The output from the last layer is normalized by the softmax function, which turns it into a probability distribution that includes the two classes. As a result, in this distribution, the class with the highest probability corresponds to the predicted class.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Files like "drowsiness_detection.py," "models.py," "alarm.wav," and three Haar cascade files for detecting face, left eye, and right eye are among the many crucial parts of the drowsiness detection system.

Import the necessary Python libraries, then use the dataset to perform driver drowsiness detection.

Drowsiness_detection.py

```
drowsiness_detection.py x model.py
1 import cv2
2 import os
3 from keras.models import load_model
4 import numpy as np
5 from pygame import mixer
6 import time
```

Model.py

```
drowsiness_detection.py model.py x
1 import os
2 from keras.preprocessing import image
3 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
4 import numpy as np
5 import random,shutil
6 from keras.models import Sequential
7 from keras.layers import Dropout,Conv2D,Flatten,Dense, MaxPooling2D, BatchNormalization
8 from keras.models import load_model
```

The first part of the code uses a pre-trained Haar cascade to identify faces in the video feed. The code uses the same method to detect the left and right eyes after identifying the face.

The region of interest (ROI) is taken out of the frame and preprocessed for each eye. The ROI is transformed into a 3D tensor, scaled to 24 by 24 pixels, normalized, and converted to grayscale.

Three haar cascade files: one for the left eye, one for the right eye, and one for the face.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

When the driver drowsiness detection system senses that the driver is sleepy, an alarm sound is played. In Python, the Pygame's mixer feature is used to implement this.

Using the mixer.init() function, the Pygame mixer is first initialized. Next, the mixer.Sound() function is used to specify the file path for the alarm sound file. The file path is specified as mixer.Sound('alarm.wav'), where the sound file's name is alarm.wav

Fig. 3

The sound.play() function is used by the system to play the alarm sound when it determines that the driver is sleepy. This is implemented in the code within the if clause, which examines whether the eyes have been closed for a predetermined number of frames. The call to the sound.stop() function ends the alarm sound. This is done in the code within

the else statement, which determines whether the eyes are open. The alarm goes off when the eyes are open.

In general, this code implements an alarm sound in the driver drowsiness detection system using the Pygame library. The alarm sound is played when the system determines that the driver is drowsy.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the machine learning and OpenCV-based driver drowsiness detection system is a practical way to detect drowsiness and reduce traffic accidents. The system uses a convolutional neural network (CNN) and Haar cascades to reliably detect the driver's eye state and discriminate between open and closed eyes. When the system determines that the driver is showing signs of drowsiness, it sets off an alarm to notify them.

The accuracy of the Haar cascades for object detection and the caliber of the dataset used to train the CNN model determine how effective the system is. However, with careful training and tuning, the system can be improved to provide higher precision and reliability. Overall, this system is a useful tool for improving traffic safety and reducing collisions caused by drowsy driving.

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